

Data Management Plan for Kenya

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Introduction

The spread of electric charging stations is essential for boosting clean transport as the globe moves towards a more sustainable future. Like many other nations, Kenya is actively pursuing the expansion of its charging infrastructure as it embraces the switch to electric vehicles (EVs). A solid data management plan is necessary to efficiently manage the data related to the deployment of electric charging stations. In order to support the expansion of the charging infrastructure and promote actions towards climate change mitigation, this plan assures the effective data collection, storage, analysis, and utilisation.

The data management plan is aimed at identifying potential EV charging locations across the nation using geospatial data. With the vision of fostering sustainable mobility, our project focuses on establishing a comprehensive network of EV charging stations that will power the future of transportation.

For successful execution of this plan, inclusion of stakeholders, policy makers and actors is very important. The plan highlights the relevant stakeholders such as regulatory bodies, government institutions that should be engaged.

By combining different geospatial data sources, the plan allows centralization of data which helps in strategically locating charging stations throughout major cities, highways, and key destinations. We aim to promote the adoption of electric vehicles across the country.

Stakeholders

Ministry of Energy

Ministry of Roads and Transport

SEforALL

Energy4Impact

Ministry of Planning

National Construction Authority (NCA)

County government (business permits)

National Environment Management Authority (NEMA)

Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (EPRA)

Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC)

BasiGo

Roam Electric

Actors

Database Administrators

Data analysts

Database Programmer

Public

Functional requirements

User Story reference	Expectation	Acceptance criteria
1	<p>Database administrator</p> <p>As a Database Administrator, I am in charge of enabling users to access the data by providing login credentials, ensuring the database is working efficiently to ease data accessibility.</p> <p>I also provide permissions when organisations need to update or edit their data.</p>	<p>When a new user creates an account, I am notified. The system should be able to send a notification to allow the user to register using a password.</p> <p>If the user is unable to log in, there should be a notification that the user needs assistance.</p> <p>When an organization needs to update the data, the admin is notified to grant permission.</p>
2	<p>Data Analysts</p> <p>As a Data Analyst, I want to have access to the data, with added filters of accessing the data e.g region, organisational.</p>	<p>When raw data is input or uploaded, the system should organise it automatically by applying the relevant filters e.g dates, organization or region.</p> <p>For data validation, there should be a link to the source of the data that can be clicked.</p> <p>Data visualization features should be available as such as graphs, tables</p>

3	<p>Public</p> <p>As a member of the public, I want to access the data . I should be able to create an account using my email.The user interface should be friendly for ease of navigation.</p>	<p>When I create an account, I should receive an email notification that my account is ready to use.</p> <p>There should be a search tab at the top or a menu where I can easily type what kind of data Im looking for</p> <p>If I am unable to login, there should be a pop up support message to provide assistance .i.e Need Help?</p> <p>When I search for information,there should be a search bar where I can type keywords and get results.</p>
4	<p>Database programmer</p> <p>As a database programmer, I run system tests to ensure the system is working properly.</p> <p>I am also responsible for upgrading the system to match current trends.</p>	<p>When the system encounters a problem, it displays an error message. This message gives more information on where the bug is to enable debugging</p> <p>When the system needs upgrading, I am notified and I undertake the necessary installation and upgrading of the system to ensure smooth running</p>

Non-functional requirements

- The system should be able to efficiently handle a high volume of spatial data.
- The system should offer quick query and data retrieval responses.
- The system should have automatic back-up functionality to avoid data loss.

Data requirements

Dataset	Source	Link	Coverage	Format	Year	Resolution	Category / Theme	Do we have already?
Roads network	World Bank	https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0041430/Kenya-Roads	National	Shape file	2017	N/A		Yes
Electrical Distribution Network	Kenya Power & Lighting Company	https://www.kplc.co.ke/	National	Shape File	2020	N/A		Yes
Global EV Data	International Energy Agency	https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-product/global-ev-outlook-2023#global-ev-data	Global	Csv File	2023	N/A		Yes

System architecture

Governance

The project steering committee consists of;

- Project Manager
- Funder
- Project Owner
- Data Analyst

Policy Guidelines

The SDI should have an open source software policy. Relevant data and standards policies applicable to the SDI must be followed to the letter. Generally, regulatory bodies must be included in the development of the SDI to promote standards and data compliance.

Quality Assurance, testing and review

There has to be a quality management team to ensure that the data is accurate and up to date. The geospatial data should be reviewed regularly by GIS staff to ensure high quality GIS data.

Monitoring and evaluation

The project steering committee is responsible for monitoring and evaluation. The agile model of product development can be adopted to ensure that every deliverable at each stage is met before proceeding to the subsequent stages. The model involves dividing the SDI development into short sprints. At the end of each sprint, team members meet to discuss and give feedback.

Hosting, support and maintenance

For ease of accessibility and backup functionality, cloud services should be used to host the database.

Capacity building and training

Activities for capacity building may include planning for future collaboration and developing leadership. Quarterly workshops can be included to train users on SDI.

Code Management

The code can be uploaded in Github to allow joint effort when working on the project.

Budget

Stakeholder funding institutions :

- World Bank
- United Nations
- Ministry of Roads and Transport

- Ministry of Energy

Work Breakdown Structure

The inclusion of an agile model of product development must consist of a work breakdown structure that breaks down high level tasks into smaller tasks to ease monitoring and evaluation procedures.